

**Standard E.M.F. of the Cell; Pt|Q.H. $\underset{(c)}{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}$ | $\underset{(c)}{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}$ | $\underset{(c)}{\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4}$; Hg_2SO_4 |Hg
and the Standard Electrode Potential of $\text{Hg}|\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ at
5°, 15°, 25° and 35°.**

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The e.m.f. of the cell;

which is given by $E = E_0 - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 f^2 \text{HfSO}_4$, has been studied from 5° to 35°. In the above cell Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. The concentration of H^+ , HSO_4^- , SO_4^{2-} and Hg_2^{2+} in the saturated solution of Hg_2SO_4 in sulphuric acid solutions have been calculated by using the method of approximations and the relationships, $\log K_A = \log K + 4A\sqrt{\mu} - \beta\mu$ and $\log K_{\text{sp}(A)} = \log K_{\text{sp}} + 8A\sqrt{\mu} - 2\beta\mu$. In the above expressions,

$$K_A = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-]}, \quad K_{\text{sp}(A)} = [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$$

and the values of A and β are the same as in previous study¹. The value of E° of the cell are found by plotting

$$E + \frac{RT}{2F} \times 2.303 \log [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] - \frac{2.303RT}{F} \times 3A\sqrt{\mu}$$

against μ . This E° which is on molarity scale, can be converted to the molality scale i.e., $E^\circ(\text{m})$, with the formula

$$E^\circ(\text{m}) = E^\circ - \frac{3RT}{2F} \ln \rho$$

where ρ is the density of the solvent at the temperature concerned. $E^\circ(\text{m})$ comes out to be -0.0850, -0.0857, -0.0863 and -0.0878 volt at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively. Since $E^\circ(\text{m})$ is the difference between the standard electrode potentials of $\text{Hg}|\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ and $\text{Pt}|\text{Q.H.}, \text{H}^+$; the values of standard electrode potential of $\text{Hg}|\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ on molality scale come out to be 0.6294, 0.6214, 0.6135 and 0.6046 at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively.

The determination of the standard electrode potential of $\text{Hg}|\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ has to be based on the dissociation constant of HSO_4^- . Since there is wide difference in the values of dissociation constant determined by various authors¹, we have determined the values of E° of the cell;

1. L. Sharma and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 241.
2. H. S. Harned and W. J. Hamer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 27; W. H. Beck, J. V. Dobson and W. F. K. Wynne-Jones, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1960, **56**, 1172; S. Sircar, P. K. Jena and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 101.

by taking the solubility of Hg_2SO_4 into account. From the $E^\circ(m)$ value, the standard electrode potential of $\text{Hg}|\text{Hg}_2\text{SO}_4, \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ has been calculated using our values¹ of dissociation constant of HSO_4^- and compared with earlier values².

EXPERIMENTAL

Sulphuric acid of analytical grade and double distilled water were used. Stock solution of sulphuric acid was prepared and standardised against borax³. Experimental solutions were prepared by diluting the stock solution to the appropriate volume at the experimental temperatures and deoxygenated with nitrogen gas as described earlier¹. Mercurous sulphate was prepared and stored as recommended by Hulett⁴. Hydrolysis of mercurous sulphate in the cell was avoided by using sulphuric acid of concentrations⁵, above 0.0008 mole/litre. In each case, the mercurous sulphate was rinsed eight times with the experimental solution before use. The electrode vessels, bridges and setting up of the cells were similar to those published in an earlier paper⁶. The temperature of the thermostat was controlled within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Measurements were made with a Bajaj Vernier Potentiometer. Duplicate experiments (mean has been given in the Tables) in case of each solution generally agreed among themselves within 0.1 mv. In a few cases the difference in the e.m.f. of the duplicates was found to be 0.15 mv. The experimental data are given in the Tables I, II, III and IV. Stoichiometric concentrations in gm moles/litre are indicated by $[\]_T$. In all the tables :

$$-X = -E \frac{RT}{2F} \times 2.303 \log [\text{H}^+]^2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \frac{2.303RT}{F} \times 3A\sqrt{\mu}.$$

TABLE I

Temperature 5°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T$	E in volt	$[\text{H}^+] \times 10^3$	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] \times 10^4$	$\mu \times 10^3$	-X
0.008	0.08822	13.75	6.05	2.96	20.69	0.08743
0.012	0.07724	19.86	8.10	2.44	28.69	0.08818
0.016	0.06965	25.67	9.88	2.13	36.19	0.08894
0.020	0.06357	31.25	11.44	1.92	43.27	0.09002
0.024	0.05907	36.66	12.84	1.76	50.02	0.09058
0.028	0.05522	41.91	14.07	1.63	56.47	0.09127
0.032	0.05154	47.03	15.19	1.53	62.68	0.09231

3. A. I. Vogel, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis" (Third Edn.), 1962, 238.
4. G. A. Hulett, *Phys. Rev.*, 1911, **32**, 257.
5. M. H. Litzky and R. W. Stoughton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5226.
6. S. Nath, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **28**, 683.

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TABLE II

Temperature 15°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T$	E in volt	$[\text{H}^+] \times 10^3$	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] \times 10^4$	$\mu \times 10^3$	-X
0.008	0.09609	13.19	5.55	3.58	19.81	0.08793
0.012	0.08499	18.97	7.27	3.04	27.15	0.08871
0.016	0.07724	24.47	8.74	2.72	34.02	0.08953
0.020	0.07139	29.77	10.02	2.50	40.55	0.09027
0.024	0.06695	34.91	11.15	2.34	46.77	0.09070
0.028	0.06284	39.93	12.15	2.21	52.74	0.09156
0.032	0.05926	44.83	13.04	2.11	58.51	0.09243

TABLE III

Temperature 25°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T$	E in volt	$[\text{H}^+] \times 10^3$	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] \times 10^4$	$\mu \times 10^3$	-X
0.008	0.10473	12.53	4.97	4.40	18.82	0.08831
0.012	0.09329	17.96	6.35	3.83	25.46	0.08937
0.016	0.08557	23.15	7.50	3.51	31.70	0.09011
0.020	0.07972	28.16	8.49	3.28	37.63	0.09078
0.024	0.07495	33.03	9.34	3.12	43.31	0.09149
0.028	0.07113	37.80	10.10	2.99	48.80	0.09199
0.032	0.06779	42.48	10.77	2.88	54.12	0.09256

TABLE IV

Temperature 35°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]_T$	E in volt	$[\text{H}^+] \times 10^3$	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] \times 10^4$	$\mu \times 10^3$	-X
0.008	0.11137	12.03	4.55	5.26	18.16	0.09041
0.012	0.10037	17.25	5.72	4.66	24.37	0.09083
0.016	0.09243	22.24	6.67	4.33	30.21	0.09167
0.020	0.08667	27.07	7.48	3.97	35.76	0.09215
0.024	0.08200	31.79	8.18	3.94	41.12	0.09267
0.028	0.07776	36.41	8.79	3.82	46.35	0.09353
0.032	0.07421	40.97	9.34	3.71	51.42	0.09425

DISCUSSION

The e.m.f. of the cell :

is given by

$$E = E^0 - \frac{RT}{2F} \ln [\text{H}^+]^2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] f^2 \text{HfSO}_4.$$

Since $\log f^2\text{HfSO}_4 = -6A\sqrt{\mu} + B\mu$, therefore

$$E + \frac{2 \cdot 303RT}{2F} \log[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}] - \frac{2 \cdot 303RT}{F} \times 3A\sqrt{\mu} = E^\circ - \frac{2 \cdot 303RT B\mu}{2F} \quad \dots (1)$$

As explained earlier¹

$$\log \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-]} = \log K_A = \log K + 4A\sqrt{\mu} - \beta\mu \quad \dots (2)$$

The values of $\log K$ and β at various temperatures have also been found out¹. The value of K_{sp} is found from the equation reported earlier⁷. It has been shown⁷ that

$$\log K_{sp} = \log [\text{Hg}_2^{2+}][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]f^2\text{SO}_4 = \log K_{sp(A)} - 8A\sqrt{\mu} + 2\beta\mu \quad \dots (3)$$

and the value of β in equation (3) is the same as in equation (2). It is evident that in a saturated solution of Hg_2SO_4 in H_2SO_4 ,

$$K_A = \frac{(1+\alpha)(\alpha c + c_1)}{(1-\alpha)} \quad \dots (4)$$

and

$$K_{sp(A)} = c_1(\alpha c + c_1) \quad \dots (5)$$

In the above equations α is the degree of dissociation of HSO_4^- and c and c_1 are the stoichiometric concentrations of H_2SO_4 and Hg_2SO_4 in gm moles/litre. As a first approximation c_1 is assumed to be zero and the value of K_A , α and μ for any concentration of H_2SO_4 are found by successive approximations with the help of equation (2). Taking this value of μ and α , $K_{sp(A)}$ is found from equation (3), and c_1 from equation (5). Now a new value of μ is calculated from the previously found value of α and the value of c_1 ; from

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2}[\text{H}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{HSO}_4^-] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + 2[\text{Hg}_2^{2+}] = \frac{1}{2}(1+\alpha)c + \frac{1}{2}(1-\alpha)c + 2(\alpha c + c_1) + 2c_1.$$

With these values of μ and c_1 new values of K_A and α are found from equations (2) and (4) respectively. Then a new value of μ is calculated with the previously found value of c_1 and the new value of α . The process is repeated to find more accurate value of μ , using equations (3) and (5) at one time and (2) and (4) at another, till μ becomes constant upto the 4th place of decimal. The values of concentrations at this stage represent the correct values. They are tested by confirming the agreement between the calculated and observed values of K and K_{sp} . The L.H.S. of equation (1) which can now be evaluated, plotted against μ , taking precautions given in earlier paper⁸, gives E_0 . The values of E° (Molarity scale) and B in equation (1) is given below :

	5°	15°	25°	35°
E°	-0.0850	-0.0857	-0.0864	-0.0880
B	4.10	3.99	3.95	3.87

7. L. Sharma and B. Prasad. (Communicated for publication to *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*). Solubility product of Hg_2SO_4 at a number of temperatures.

8. L. Sharma, G. Sahu and B. Prasad, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 580.

The value of E° if molality has been used i.e., $E^\circ(m)$ can be found from equation :

$$E^\circ(m) = E^\circ - \frac{3RT}{2F} \times 2.303 \log \rho$$

where ρ is the density of solvent and $E^\circ(m)$ at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° thus comes out to be -0.0850, -0.0857, -0.0863 and -0.0878 volt respectively. The accepted value of standard electrode potential⁹ of quinhydrone electrode on molality scale are 0.7144, 0.7071, 0.6998 and 0.6924 volt at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively. So the values of standard electrode potential of Hg|Hg₂SO₄, SO₄²⁻ on the molality scale come out to be 0.6294, 0.6214, 0.6135 and 0.6046 volt at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively. These values (Harned and Hamer's 0.6310, 0.6231, 0.6152 and 0.6070 at the four temperatures and Prasad and co-workers 0.6025 at 35°) do not agree with those of earlier workers². This is due to the fact that earlier values are either based on the second dissociation constant of H₂SO₄ which are not correct or are vitiated because hydrolysis of Hg₂SO₄ in water has been neglected. It may be pointed out that if the solubility correction for Hg₂SO₄ had not been made the values of E_0 would have been 0.2 to 0.25 mv lower than those given in this paper.

The authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the research grant and for the award of fellowship to one of them (L.S.) and to the authorities of Patna University for library and laboratory facilities.

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Received January 20, 1969

9. R. G. Bates. "Electrometric pH Determinations", p. 175, Wiley, New York, 1954.